

EFFECTIVENESS OF THE USING INTERACTIVE METHODS IN PRIMARY SCHOOLS

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Abstract.

The article emphasizes the importance of using interactive methods in primary education and their effectiveness in the classroom.

Keywords: interactive method, role plays, brainstorming, case-study method, presentations and discussions.

BOSHLANG'ICH TA'LIM YO'NALISHLARIDA INTERFAOL METODLARNING FOYDALANISH SAMARASI.

Annotatsiya.

Maqolada boshlang'ich ta'lim yo'nalishlarida interfaol metodlardan foydalanishning ahamiyatlari va ularning darsdagi samarasi to'g'risida fikrlar keltirib o'tilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: interfaol metodlar, rolli o'yinlar, aqliy hujum, keys-stadi usuli, taqdimotlar va muhokamalar.

ПРЕИМУЩЕСТВА ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЯ ИНТЕРАКТИВНЫХ МЕТОДОВ В НАЧАЛЬНЫХ ШКОЛА.

Аннотация.

В статье подчеркивается важность использования интерактивных методов в начальном образовании и их эффективность на уроках.

Ключевые слова: интерактивные методы, ролевые игры, мозговой штурм, кейс-метод, презентация и дискуссия.

The teaching of English as a foreign language is now one of the most important subjects in most European primary schools. The implementation of English has brought along the need to establish clear objectives that are different to the ones traditionally assigned to secondary schools. While in secondary schools we still find, in many cases, a teaching based in the formal aspects of the language, i.e. grammar; primary school teachers have had to adopt a different approach as the age of the children make the teaching of formal aspects not advisable. As a result of this point of view, the different Educational Departments have decided to establish, as the main purpose of the EFL teaching, the development of the four skills: listening, speaking, reading and writing. However, the implementation of this approach has not been trouble-free as many teachers insist on asking their children to understand every single word they listen to or read, or expect their pupils to write or speak without making the mistakes normally found in the process of acquiring any language.

The rapid development of modern society compels a student to learn and understand the material quickly, especially a foreign language. Nowadays, mastering at least one foreign language is becoming integral requirement for the professional competence of a specialist. Therefore, it is necessary to pay attention to the efficiency and quality of the process of learning foreign languages. The most effective methods of learning languages are interactive methods.

The term "interactive" means that people work together and have an influence on each other. This situation implies a dialogue or a conversation. Therefore, these methods are aimed at the interaction between students and the teacher as well as

among students only. It requires an active role of students in the learning process.

The purpose of the interactive learning is to create some special conditions leading to the involvement of all the students into the learning process in which the participants can understand and realize everything that happens, influence each other and make their own contribution having established the friendly and mutually supportive relationship.

The most popular methods are **role plays, brainstorming, case-study method, presentations and discussions**. They develop communicative skills, logical thinking and different types of intellectual activity such as analysis, synthesis, comparison, and generalization. These student-centered methods are highly appropriate, particularly for involving students more actively in acquiring knowledge, skills and strategies.

There are some activities in the spotlight:

- ▶ Structured and unstructured.
- ▶ Reverse or negative thinking.
- ▶ Nominal group relationships.
- ▶ Online interaction such as chat, forums and email.
- ▶ Team-idea mapping.
- ▶ Group passing.
- ▶ Individual brainstorming.

Some primary school teachers have introduced a lot of teaching styles and classroom activities and have come up with very encouraging results. Both parents and teachers find that there is a big leap in children's language proficiency and their desire to learn. Above all, pupils involved find English lessons more enjoyable as the activities are interesting and enable them to express their ideas in creative ways.

There are 10 interactive teaching styles that make a difference

1. *Find the differences (25 mins)*
2. *Picture crossword : Parts of the body (20 mins)*

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3. *True or false? (20-25 mins)*
4. *Who's who in family? (logic problem 15 mins)*
5. *How do they look? (20 mins)*
6. *Making sentences (20-25 mins)*
7. *Jigsaw reading (20mins)*
8. *Role- playing(15mins)*
9. *Running dictation (20mins)*
10. *Ice Breakers (15 mins)*

It is important to keep the activities varied in primary schools and not to spend too long on any one thing. Try to find material that is relevant to them. For example, it wouldn't be appropriate to base a lesson for pupils on renting and furnishing an apartment. The following subjects are always popular:

- The internet
- Celebrities
- Music
- Sports
- Fashion
- The media

But don't underestimate your pupils – they can deal with more serious subjects too and are often very concerned about world issues. Classroom activities well if you are teaching in primary schools, and they also help them learn about working as a team. The following activities are always good choices:

- ▶ **1. Think, pair and share.** Set a problem or a question around a certain topic, and pair up your students. Give each pair of students enough time so they can reach a proper conclusion, and permit the kids to share their conclusion in their voice. This way your students will be engaged, communicating, and remember more of the class than ever before.
- ▶ **2. Brainstorming.** Interactive brainstorming is mostly performed in group sessions. The process is useful for generating creative thoughts and ideas.

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Brainstorming helps students learn to work together, and above all, learn from each other. You'll be surprised by all the great ideas they come up with!

▶ **3. Buzz session.** Participants come together in session groups that focus on a single topic. Within each group, every student contributes thoughts and ideas.

Encourage discussion and collaboration among the students within each group. Everyone should learn from each other's input and experiences. As a teacher, you could give your students some keywords to spark the conversation.

▶ **4. Pick the Winner.** Divide the class into groups and let them work on the same topic/problem. Let them record an answer/strategy on paper or digitally.

Then, ask the groups to switch with a nearby group and let them evaluate their answer. After a few minutes, allow each set of groups to merge and ask them to select the best answer from the two choices, which will be presented to the complete class.

▶ **5. Movie Application** In groups, students discuss examples of movies that made use of a concept or event discussed in class, trying to identify at least one way the movie makers got it right, and one way they got it wrong. Think about movies showing historical facts, geographical facts, biographies of famous people,.

▶ **6. Scrabble.** Use the chapter (or course) title as the pool of letters from which to make words (e.g., mitochondrial DNA), and allow teams to brainstorm as many words relevant to the topic as possible. You can also actually play scrabble and ask students to form words from the newly learned vocabulary.

▶ **7. Who/what am I?** Tape a term or name on the back of each student. You can also tape it on their forehead. Each student walks around the room, asking "yes or no" questions to the other students in an effort to guess the term. Of course, the term has something to do with your lesson topic.

▶ **8. Crossword puzzle.** The crossword game is perfect to use as repetition activity. Choose a list of words and their description, and Book Widgets creates an interactive crossword for you. The crossword game transforms these boring lessons into a fun experience.

► **9. Board rotation.** This interactive learning strategy is even more interactive than others! Divide your class into different groups of students and assign them to each of the boards you've set up in the room. Assign one topic/question per board. After each group writes an answer, they rotate to the next board. Here, they write their answer below the first answer of the previous group. Let them go around the room until all the groups have covered all the boards. Not that many boards in your classroom? Try using tablets and Book Widgets' interactive whiteboard.

► **10. Optimist/Pessimist** In pairs, students take opposite emotional sides of a case study, statement, or topic. Encourage them to be empathic and truly “live” the case study. You'll discover some good solution proposals and your students will learn some exceptional social skills.

Great teachers are nimble, observant, and responsive, always keeping an open mind about how to best engage their students and get them excited about learning—and that means considering trying out different *interactive* teaching styles in the classroom.

Interactive teaching styles are designed around a simple principle: without practical application, students often fail to comprehend the depths of the study material. Interactive teaching is also beneficial for you as the teacher in a number of ways, including:

- **Measurable student accomplishments:** Teachers making use of interactive teaching styles are better equipped to assess how well students master a given subject material.
- **Flexibility in teaching:** Applying training methods that involve two-way communications will enable you to make quick adjustments in processes and approaches.
- **Practice makes perfect:** Interactive instruction enhances the learning process.
- **Student motivation:** Two-way teaching dispels student passivity, and when more students are engaged, you'll have much more fun too.

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Whereas students often lose interest during lecture-style teaching, interactive teaching styles promote an atmosphere of attention and participation. Make it interesting. Make it exciting. Make it fun. As you well know, telling is not teaching and listening is not learning.

- Encourage student participation
- Use questions that stimulate response, discussion, and a hands-on experience.
- Use teaching aids that press for answers, and capture/hold the student's attention.
- Set up a workgroup environment.
- Involve yourself as well as the student.

Teaching English to teenagers is great fun. It can be inspiring for the students and the teacher alike, and it opens up a completely new area of employment for you to consider.

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